

Extracurricular Activities as a Form of Development of Social Competence of Adolescents with Intellectual Disorders

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Abstract: The formation and development of social competence of adolescents with intellectual disabilities is a priority of special educational institutions, because it is the key to successful socialization of these students. The main goal is to reveal the psychological and pedagogical conditions for the formation of social competence of adolescents with intellectual disabilities through their engagement into the extracurricular activities. The method involves considering the capabilities of each teenager in extracurricular activities at any age. Extracurricular activities that are based on each individual case of every student are used to form specific competencies that are especially important for him at the next level of learning and socialization. The experiment involved 114 adolescents aged 12-16 years studying in special educational institutions. Based on the components of social competence, the following methods were selected and diagnostics were performed: projective technique “Incomplete Sentences”, projective drawing “My Friends”, observation, exploratory technique “My Orientations”, exploratory technique “Nonverbal characteristics of communication”, observation, Saul Rosenzweig test, exploratory technique “An Island”, projective technique “Joint Drawing”, drama game “The Turnip”, exploratory technique “Assess the Behavior”, a discussion based on short stories “The Hero’s Character and His Actions”. The number of adolescents with intellectual disabilities who have cognitive-related competencies has increased significantly ($t=5,01$; $p=0,001$); competencies of motivational and value sphere ($t=4,7$; $p=0,01$). Increased was the number of adolescents who adequately assess themselves and their abilities and capabilities (33, 85%), use socially acceptable behavior and understand moral norms (39, 47%). The level of control over students’ own actions has significantly increased, as well as their ability to evaluate their own actions and self-reflect ($t = 5.3$; $p = 0.05$). The diagnostic results obtained after the introduction of the method testified to the effectiveness of its use for adolescents with intellectual disabilities in the conditions of special educational institutions.

Keywords: *method of cases; psychological and pedagogical conditions; educational process; special education institutions; psychophysical disorders.*

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Introduction

Current changes in the educational paradigm of the New Ukrainian School provide new requirements for the training of the graduates of special education institutions, particularly, the development and formation of a competent personality in order to successfully socialize and integrate into society. The New Ukrainian School normative documents determine the social standards for graduates of educational institutions, particularly special educational institutions – students’ mastering social competencies by establishing the interrelationship between classroom and extracurricular activities, the further based on the above formation of the new personal qualities and norms of behavior.

Ukrainian scientists, while highlighting the priority issues of education and upbringing of children with intellectual disabilities, have determined that half (56.4%) of students of special education institutions and of training and rehabilitation centers have problems with communication with adults and peers, difficulties in assimilating moral norms (Shishmentsev, 2017). 38% of students do not know how to make independent decisions and resolve conflict situations by themselves (Bystrova, 2007). 45.7% of students with intellectual disabilities are not able to control their own behavior, prone to aggression and impulsive actions, cannot establish social connections (Rudenko, 2013). Therefore, the formation of social competence of adolescents with intellectual disabilities is an urgent problem of modern Ukrainian education, which, in our opinion, is advisable to solve in the process of organizing the extracurricular activities of the students.

Social competence is considered by us in pedagogical, psychological and defectological (special education) aspects. The essence of the competence approach in pedagogical science was addressed by Popovych (2019), Khokhlina (2018) and others. Scientists of psychological and pedagogical direction consider the phenomenology of social competence as an individual quality of personality, which allows a person to integrate into society, to form value and moral norms of personality, its attitude to oneself and others (Popovych, 2019). Social competence allows individuals to evolve and be successful at the household, professional, socio-economic, family and other levels of social life (Khokhlina, O., 2018; Synyov et al., 2008).

In special education, competence is viewed as a set of personal qualities and skills of socially approved behavior acquired in the process of correctional and educational measures, as a component of successful socialization of people with psychophysical disorders (Khokhlina, 2018;

Synyov et al., 2000; Synyov et al, 2008); formation of professional skills and abilities of people with intellectual disorders (Bystrova, 2007; Shishmentsev, 2017).

The works of V. Synyov, O. Pometun, V. Kryvusha, M. Suprun, (2000) are devoted to the question of the influence of the content and forms of extracurricular activities on the development of social competence of adolescents.

In our study we consider the extracurricular activities as the main area of interaction in the teacher-student system, which is based on the needs and interests of students, their own choice of different activities, except educational, in various areas of possible integration of adolescents into society (sports, arts, health, leisure, entertainment community work), which can be implemented in development programs, competitions, excursions, art clubs, sports sections and patriotic events, creates a comfortable environment for the student and provides him with a situation of success in the significant for adolescents activities. Success in the leading activities provides, in turn, the development of personality (Gerasymova, 2019; Melnyk, 2019; Nerubasska, 2020; Sheremet, 2019; Synyov et al., 2000).

The objective of the study is to reveal the psychological and pedagogical conditions for the formation of social competence of adolescents with intellectual disabilities during extracurricular activities.

Material & methods

The study was conducted during 2017-2019 and included 2 stages. The experiment involved 114 adolescents studying in special educational institutions of Kherson, Cherkasy, Zakarpattia, Luhansk and Ternopil regions, respondents aged 12-16 years.

At the first stage (2017-2018) the author's method of formation and development of social competence of adolescents with intellectual disabilities was introduced and tested on the basis of real situations (cases) during extracurricular activities, preliminary diagnostics was carried out in experimental and control groups.

At the second stage (2018-2019) the results of the implementation of the methodology were analyzed, the ways of further research were outlined.

The method of forming the social competence of adolescents with intellectual disabilities in extracurricular activities using the method of cases was presented by three blocks, which, in our opinion, should be exploited

within the framework of competence-based, personality-oriented, systemically-active and axiological approaches:

1. Motivation and value block is represented by methodological principles, which are the main conditions for the formation of social competence of adolescents: the principle of the interrelation between lessons and extracurricular activities; the principle of systematization, consistency and continuity of the educational process in a special educational institution; the principle of personality-oriented learning.

2. Activity block is represented by the method of formation of social competence on the basis of real cases. The implementation of the method depends on the following factors (educational institution, family circle, educational environment, peers, personal experience of each student, his individual personal qualities) and the main mechanisms of formation of social competencies (internalization, identification, self-reflection, imitation, motivation, etc.). Types of extracurricular activities - real social situations, cases, social trainings, drama plays, collective holidays, festivals, competitions, thematic decades, sports contests, interesting meetings, creative workshops, educational clubs, flash mobs, etc.

3. Evaluation and summarizing block – diagnostics of the efficiency of social and pedagogical conditions of the introduction of the method and level of formation of social competence of teenagers after its introduction (summative and final diagnostics).

At the ascertaining stage of experimental work the basic components of social competence were defined:

- motivational and value component – a teenager is able to cooperate, recognizes the value of constructive strategies for resolving situations, able to cooperate with adults and peers; comprehends his own worthiness, is able to establish social connections, is motivated to communicate;

- cognitive component – the teenager is able to work in a team and under direction, shows socially acceptable behavior, knows ways to resolve conflict situations, understands and experiences different emotions, understands the facial expressions of the opponent, uses nonverbal communication, distinguishes what are mood, feelings and emotions;

- activity component – a teenager is able to present his own achievements and interests, shows responsibility, is able to control mistakes in his activities, is able to listen to adults and peers, is able to control his own behavior and emotional state, knows and does sport exercises, is capable to lead a healthy lifestyle;

- assessment component – a teenager is able to provide a correct assessment of the situation, evaluate the behavior of others, choose a behavior having considered the situation.

Based on the components of social competence, the following methods were selected and diagnostics were performed:

- motivational and value component – Rene Gille (1959) film test, Philip projective method in Bystrova's (2007) adaptation “Incomplete Sentences”, projective drawing “My Friends” (Kolodna et al., 2017), observations, method “My Orientations” (Kolodna et al., 2017);

- cognitive component – method of V. Labunskaya (1986) “Non-verbal characteristics of communication”, observation, Saul Rosenzweig test (Lukin & Suvorov, 1993);

- activity component –Bystrova (2007) method “An Island”, projective technique “Joint Drawing” (Bystrova, 2007), drama game “The Turnip” (Kudryashova, 2017);

- assessment component – exploratory technique “Assess the Behavior” (Kurganova & Karabanova, 2004), an author’s structured discussion based on short stories “The Hero’s Character and His Actions” (Shishmentsev, 2017).

Among the others the following methods were used: theoretical - analysis of psychological, pedagogical and special literature in order to determine the state of development of the problem and perspective areas for its solution. Empirical methods - observation, pedagogical projection, method of cases, situation modeling, method of expert assessments. Statistical methods: quantitative and qualitative processing of research results, comparative analysis by Student's *t*-test to prove the significance of differences between results before and after the implementation of the method.

Analysis of the results of the ascertaining experiment showed low indicators of social competence of adolescents in both groups in all components. Particularly low level of the assessment component (5.92% in the experimental group (EG), and 5.77% in the control group (CG). 9.47% of EG adolescents and 9.65% of CG adolescents had a low level of development of moral norms, behavioral disorders and troubles in the interpersonal relationships.

On the basis of the received initial diagnostic data on the suggested components we have defined the social and psychological conditions to introduce the method of formation of social competence of the teenagers with intellectual disabilities. The effectiveness of the method during the extracurricular activities was ensured by its systematic, gradual, continuous

and consistent implementation; creating an interconnection between lessons and extracurricular activities; creation of a unified developmental and educational space in the system “family – school”; creation of a “Parent University” of social competencies; taking into account the age, psychophysical and individual characteristics of adolescents; creating individual cases with specific social situations to solve and consolidate the knowledge gained at school and educational classes, in order to form their social competencies.

At the second stage, taking into account the obtained diagnostic data, the method of formation of social competencies of adolescents in extracurricular activities was implemented. On the basis of real cases, students were provided with knowledge about the organization of group work, resolving conflicts, difficult life situations and situations of frustration. Adolescents learned to talk about themselves, present their own achievements and abilities, share their own interests, be responsible for their own actions and behavior, analyze the results of their own activities and activities and behavior of their peers, learned to control their own emotional state; to plan and project the future with the help of teachers, make over time action plans.

Implementation of the methodology included: teachers creating the cases for extracurricular work on the material studied at school and supported by practical activities in author's specially created trainings for small groups; the connection between classroom work and extracurricular activities; actualization of basic knowledge before solving cases; exploitation of different methods of communication in the systems consisting of student-student and student-teacher; individual motivation for each adolescent, taking into account his interests and aptitudes; independent work of students during the process of resolving the problematic situation; demonstration of algorithms for solving complex problems (conflict situations, situations of creating social ties); creation by teachers of a model of communication and interpersonal cooperation while performing tasks.

Areas of work with cases for methodical councils of teachers:

- Natural Sciences council – correction of the child's specific perception of the environment, social adaptation of the child among peers, the formation of normative behavior and competence necessary for independent living;
- Aesthetic and Human Sciences council – the development of speech activity in the system of social relations, the formation of nationally conscious morality, spirituality;

- Mathematics council – practical focus on the use of knowledge in everyday life, self-determination, the formation of informational, communicative and creative competencies.

Cases of real situations were implemented according to the chapters of the methodology:

Chapter 1 – “Me and My World” (the tasks in this case created the conditions under which adolescents can best learn about their own world, their own feelings);

Chapter 2 – “ My Friends and I” (in the tasks for this case we created the conditions in which adolescents could best learn about interpersonal relationships, communication skills, conflict resolution, and social networking)

Chapter 3 – “Me in the Adult World” (the tasks of the case created conditions under which adolescents can best learn about relationships and features of communication with adults - teachers, parents, the assimilation of socially acceptable behavior).

Trainings on case studies were organized for teachers of special secondary schools.

Results

To determine the level of formation of social competence of adolescents with intellectual disabilities after the introduction of the method at the summative stage in the experimental group and the control group we compared the figures before and after the introduction of the method through the main components: motivational and value component, cognitive component, activity component and self-assessment component. This allowed us to identify the percentage of adolescents who have mastered the competencies according to certain criteria. The results of the implementation of the methodology - the formation of the following social competencies of adolescents at the summative stage are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The Effectiveness of Formation of Social Competencies of Adolescents with Intellectual Disabilities Before and After the Implementation of the Methodology

Groups	Before the implementation of the methodology	After the implementation of the methodology	t/p
Experimental Group			
Motivational and value component	8,77 %	39,47 %	4,7/0,01

Cognitive component	9,65 %	55,26 %	5,01/0,001
Activity component	15,26 %	36,85%	3,95/0,01
Self-assessment component	5,77 %	33,85 %	5,3/0,05
Control Group			
Motivational and value component	8,61 %	9,47 %	0,99/0,05
Cognitive component	9,48 %	11,51 %	1,8/0,05
Activity component	15,54 %	17,85 %	1,1/0,05
Self-assessment component	5,92 %	7,63 %	1,7/0,05

Systematized by the author

Therefore, after the implementation of the methodology we received a significantly increased level of the stated competencies of adolescents with intellectual disabilities in the experimental group. The number of adolescents with intellectual disabilities who obtained cognitive competencies increased significantly ($t = 5.01$; $p = 0.001$); motivational and value sphere ($t = 4.7$; $p = 0.01$); the number of adolescents who adequately evaluate themselves and their abilities and capabilities (33, 85%), use socially acceptable behavior and understand moral norms (39, 47%); significantly increased the level of control over their own actions, the ability to evaluate their own activities, self-reflections ($t = 5.3$; $p = 0.05$).

In the control group, the indicators of social competence in the described spheres have not changed.

Discussions

Similar studies are presented in the works of Ukrainian defectologists. Accordingly, in the work of I. Shishmentsev (2017) described is the method of formation of moral competencies of teenagers with intellectual disabilities during Ukrainian literature classes. The author uses interactive methods of working with adolescents, introduces elements of theatrical performances (Shishmentsev, 2017). In the research of Y. Bystrova (2012) the methods of formation of professional-labor competence of students of special educational institutions within the framework of vocational guidance work and training of mild technologies are presented. The author introduces into practice the work with adolescents with intellectual disabilities, drama games, trainings, discussion of situations after

watching movies on a given topic (Bystrova, 2012). The method of cases has not yet been the subject of special education research in terms of the formation of competencies of people with intellectual disabilities. Our author's method of using specific social situations to form the social competencies of adolescents with intellectual disabilities differs from traditional methods presented in the research of Ukrainian scientists. The particular difference is that while the students are solving cases, the teachers have the opportunity to simultaneously form any social competence and to control the level of its formation in the adolescent. Moreover, for the first time in practice of correctional education, we have declared that the developmental environment for the formation of competencies is not going to be the correctional classes, but the extracurricular activities.

Conclusions

Thus, in this article on the basis of the theoretical analysis of the last researches within the limits of the competence approach we have defined the basic criteria of social competence. We have substantiated the method of its formation in adolescents with intellectual disabilities during the extracurricular activities. Also, we have revealed the phenomenology of the concept of “extracurricular activities”. A method of forming social competencies based on the creation of cases during the extracurricular activities has been developed and implemented. It is proved that the effectiveness of the method is ensured by its systematic, gradual, continuous and consistent implementation; creating the interconnection of classroom activities, extracurricular activities and parental influence; creation of a unified developmental and educational space; taking into account the age, psychophysical and individual characteristics of adolescents; creation of individual cases with specific social situations in order to form social competencies of adolescents. The diagnostic results obtained after the introduction of the method testified to the effectiveness of its application to adolescents with intellectual disabilities in special educational institutions.

The results obtained in the study do not claim to be a comprehensive review of the problem. The accumulated data should be used in creating a methodology for the formation of social competencies of primary school students with special educational needs.

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